

Summary

Since the start of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine in February 2022, numerous efforts have been made to forge a diplomatic path towards peace. So far, these efforts have failed to produce a political settlement to the conflict, let alone a functioning ceasefire. The belligerents – Russia and Ukraine – have widely diverging views of the conflict's underlying causes, what it would take to bring it to an end, and what the terms of a negotiated settlement should be.

It is important to keep in mind that Russia's armed aggression against Ukraine did not start in 2022. It started in 2014, when Russia occupied the Crimean Peninsula and launched what came to be known as "the Donbas war". In the period between April 2014 and February 2022, this conflict claimed more than 14,000 lives. A significant share of these lives were lost after the signing of two ceasefire agreements known as "Minsk I" and "Minsk II", signed in September 2014 and February 2015. Much to the frustration of the agreements' Western backers, these ceasefire agreements remained largely unimplemented throughout the following eight years. On February 24, 2022, Russia launched a full-scale invasion of Ukraine.

To get better and deeper understanding of the causes of the current war, as well as the seemingly insurmountable obstacles to a negotiated settlement, one needs to examine why and how previous diplomatic efforts to end Russia's war have failed. Drawing on theoretical insights from the negotiation studies literature, this policy brief seeks to shed light on the diplomatic processes that preceded the signing of the Minsk agreements, as well as the practical difficulties that the parties were facing, and created for each other, in the implementation phase.

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Key Messages

- ⇒ Ceasefire negotiations are not always carried out in good faith. While trying to create a public perception that they are committed to negotiations, *the parties may try to use the process for other purposes.*
- ⇒ A militarily stronger actor may try to capitalize on battlefield gains and force a militarily weaker opponent into accepting unfavorable peace terms.
- ⇒ At any point during a negotiation process, the parties involved may find it to be in their interest to opt for the “no-deal” alternative, particularly if they believe that that time is on their side, or that a military victory may be within reach.
- ⇒ As armed conflicts progress and the parties inflict increasingly painful losses on each other, they tend to become less willing to compromise at the negotiation table, due to the involved political costs.
- ⇒ When the parties are in the endgame phase of a negotiation process and have found some common ground, they face the difficult task of turning their understanding into a written agreement.
- ⇒ In this situation, calls may be made for the inclusion of precise formulations that leave little room for interpretation.
- ⇒ At the same time, negotiators know that the negotiation process may flounder if they insist on specific formulations that their counterparts find unacceptable.
- ⇒ In some situations, they may instead choose to opt for ambiguous formulations which allow for more than one interpretation, since this may aid the process toward a consensus.
- ⇒ The problem with the “constructive ambiguity” approach is that irreconcilable differences in the interpretation of a signed agreement may delay, complicate, or even derail the agreement’s implementation.
- ⇒ The failed 2014–2022 Minsk process, which ultimately ended with Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine, provides valuable lessons and insights that may inform current and future diplomatic efforts to end Russia’s war in Ukraine.

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Background

As early as in the 18th century, Prussian King Frederick the Great is credited with the observation that “diplomacy without arms is like music without instruments”. As instruments of foreign policy, military force and diplomacy can mutually support each other. A militarily powerful actor may seek to leverage battlefield successes to compel a militarily weaker counterpart to accept a negotiated settlement that favors the former rather than the latter.

It should be emphasized, however, that asymmetries in military power are not always static. As an armed conflict progresses and evolves, the battlefield momentum may shift. This may in turn affect the dynamics of ceasefire negotiations and the negotiators’ willingness to compromise or make political concessions.

The large and growing “negotiation studies” literature may be a good starting point for analyses of the interplay between diplomacy and military power, and the practices and pitfalls of ceasefire negotiations, such as those that have been carried out between Russia and Ukraine since 2014. In a sophisticated typology of negotiation objectives, published in 1964, the Swiss-born sociologist Fred Charles Iklé described the phenomenon of “negotiations for side effects”, that is, a situation in which governments enter and carry out negotiations for purposes other than that of achieving an implementable agreement (Iklé 1964, pp. 43–58). While creating a public perception that they are committed to negotiations, the parties may try to use the process simply to obtain information that they can benefit from, or use as a propaganda tool, for instance to influence third parties, whether it be domestic or foreign audiences.

Negotiations typically go through several stages. In the “diagnostic phase” (Odell 2013, p. 384), parties conduct separate preparations and approach their counterpart(s) to explore the possibility of formalized discussions. Once at the negotiation table, they proceed to the “substance phase”, where they jointly search for common ground, with or without the help of external facilitators. The purpose of this stage of the process is to establish a framework for the subsequent “detail phase” (Odell 2013, p. 384), also known as the “endgame” or “closure phase” (Zartman 2019, p. 3), during which negotiators try to bring the process to a closure in the form of a mutually acceptable written agreement.

In some situations, negotiators may choose to opt for ambiguous formulations, since this may aid the process towards a consensus. This phenomenon is known in the literature as “constructive ambiguity” (Troitskiy 2019, p. 241). The problem with the ambiguity approach is, of course, that irreconcilable differences in the interpretation of a signed agreement may delay, prolong, or undermine the agreement’s implementation.

If and when agreement is reached and a protocol is signed, the process is by no means over. Then starts the fourth, and often most difficult, stage, which we can call “the implementation phase”. Though formally not a part of the negotiation process, the implementation phase is a critical part of the whole exercise. Ultimately, the success or failure of the implementation phase determines the success or failure of the negotiated settlement.

As time goes by and conditions change, previously agreed-upon terms may come to be seen as renegotiable. The provisions of a signed agreement may be applied in a selective manner or just ignored. As noted in previous times by U.S. arms control negotiators (see Schechter 1998, pp. 108–109), the Russian negotiating behavior is often characterized by a tendency to view the signing of an agreement not as the end result of a negotiation, but rather as a stage in an extended process.

At any point during a ceasefire or peace negotiation, the involved parties may find it to be in their interest to opt for a no-deal alternative, particularly if they believe that that time is on their side, or

that a military victory may be within reach. They may also use the tool of military escalation to worsen the no-deal option for the adversary. If one or more of the parties believe that they can obtain their objectives more effectively or rapidly by other means, this may lower the perceived costs of a non-settlement.

Why did the Minsk Process fail?

There are two main schools of thought regarding the underlying causes of the parties' failure to implement the Minsk agreements (for a detailed discussion, see Åtland 2024). One attributes non-implementation primarily to flaws in the agreements' design, while the other emphasizes "spoiler events" in the seven-year period between February 2015 and the start of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022.

If we start with the agreement-specific explanations, one of the things that are striking to an outside observer is the vagueness and ambiguity of the language used in the agreements. At the negotiating table in Minsk, the parties had been struggling to locate what I have called islands of agreement in an ocean of disagreement. The efforts were complicated by Ukraine and Russia's widely diverging views of the conflict's nature and causes, and of who should or should not be present at the table as parties.

What happened was that the parties decided to opt for loose formulations that allowed for more than one interpretation. The Ukrainians would certainly say that the agreed-upon withdrawal of "all foreign armed formations, military equipment, as well as mercenaries" (article 10 of Minsk II) should be interpreted as a reference to Russian regular troops and paramilitaries on Ukrainian soil. The Russians, for their part, would take this as a reference to Ukrainian government forces and volunteers. The vagueness and ambiguity of the language did not make the implementation easy.

Another major obstacle was the problem of how to sequence the various measures listed in them, particularly the military and political measures. Russia's preferred roadmap to peace in the Donbas would start with political measures such as the enactment of a general amnesty law in the so-called people's republics of Donetsk and Luhansk (DNR and LNR), the holding on local elections on DNR/LNR terms, validated by Kyiv, and the adoption of a "special status" law, enshrined in the Ukrainian Constitution.

Conversely, the Ukrainian side would have liked to see a full implementation of the agreements' military provisions (ceasefire, withdrawal of illegal forces, exchange of prisoners, and restoration of Ukrainian border control) before implementation of the political measures (including local elections and "special status" legislation). Kyiv's argument was that it is near impossible to conduct OSCE-observable local elections in the separatist-held regions without a functioning ceasefire, and in a situation where Ukraine's eastern border is controlled by Russian/separatist forces.

A third issue had to do with the Minsk agreements' legal status and authority, or lack thereof. Minsk I and II were not signed by the heads of state of Russia and Ukraine, or even the heads of international agencies. Nor were they signed at the level of foreign ministers. The agreements were signed by a former Ukrainian president, acting as a diplomat with the rank of ambassador, by Russia's ambassador to Ukraine, and by the unelected leaders of the two self-proclaimed "republics." The fifth signatory was the OSCE's Special Representative on Ukraine.

Minsk I and II were essentially political arrangements rather than international treaties. This does not necessarily mean that they were "illegal" or "non-binding." The creation of hybrid political-legal documents like these is a quite common international practice. And compared to Minsk I, the Minsk II

agreement enjoyed a somewhat higher degree of authority and status, stemming in part from the fact that it was endorsed in the form of a UN Security Council resolution, adopted shortly after its signing in February 2015.

Political Spoilers (2015–2022)

When it comes to the issue of political developments in the period between 2015 and 2022 that may have complicated the implementation of the Minsk accords, or even served as spoilers, three stand out as particularly relevant – Ukraine’s “de-occupation” law, adopted in 2018, Russia’s “passportization” initiative, launched in 2019, and Russia’s formal recognition of DNR and LNR as “independent states” in February 2022.

The first of these developments was largely the result of Ukrainian frustration with the lack of progress in the implementation of the Minsk agreements, and Russia’s numerous violations of the agreed-upon ceasefire. In January 2018, the Ukrainian Parliament made a move to “rebrand” the conflict. In a new piece of Ukrainian legislation, popularly known as “the Donbas de-occupation law,” the lawmakers made clear that Russia exercised “general effective control” in the territories outside Kyiv’s control. The term “temporarily occupied” became a part of the standard vocabulary, and Russia was designated as “the aggressor state”. Interestingly, the new law contained no explicit references to the Minsk accords. Such references occurred in earlier drafts but were removed ahead of the second reading of the law, after heated debates in the parliament.

An additional obstacle to the implementation of the Minsk agreements arose in the spring of 2019, when Vladimir Putin introduced a simplified procedure for the granting of Russian citizenship to residents of DNR and LNR. Russia’s “passport expansionism” in Ukraine has many similarities with the way in which this instrument has been used elsewhere in the post-Soviet space, most notably in Abkhazia, South Ossetia, and Transnistria. In the case of Donbas, the move aggravated the already strained relations between Kyiv and Moscow. In addition, it gave Russia a reason to maintain, and even increase, its military presence in Donetsk and Luhansk, for the alleged purpose of “defending Russia’s citizens”.

Throughout the fall of 2021, the Russia-Ukraine relationship went from bad to worse. Russia started massing troops and military equipment near the Ukrainian border, and it became increasingly clear that Russia was in the process of preparing for a new incursion into Ukraine, significantly more large-scale than the one in 2014. In mid-February 2022, the Russian Duma urged President Putin to recognize DNR and LNR as “self-sustained, sovereign and independent states”. The recognition followed shortly after, on February 21. Almost simultaneously, Russia started to conclude “bilateral agreements” with the new quasi-states and began to openly deploy military forces to their territory. Three days later, on February 24, Russia embarked on a large-scale invasion of Ukraine.

In hindsight, it can be argued that the Minsk agreements were neither efficient, nor fair, nor durable. They were imposed on Ukraine at the barrel of a gun, in situations where Russian/separatist forces were making territorial gains and pushing Ukrainian forces on the defensive. The fierce battles of Ilovaisk (7 August – 2 September 2014) and Debaltseve (14 January – 20 February 2015) were the backdrop against which the Minsk I and Minsk II agreements were negotiated, respectively, in September 2014 and February 2015. Russia was using the tool of military escalation instrumentally to force Kyiv to make political concessions at the negotiation table.

Ukraine was also under significant pressure from the Western backers of the Minsk process, most notably Germany and France, to accept a compromise solution to the conflict. Throughout the

negotiation process, the terms of the negotiated agreements became increasingly favorable to Russia's interests, and increasingly unfavorable to Ukraine's. This was particularly the case with the transition from Minsk I to Minsk II in February 2015. And rather than improving Ukraine's position, the Steinmeier formula, launched in October 2015, cemented the terms agreed upon in Minsk.

Lessons to be learned

As for lessons that may be learned from the unsuccessful diplomatic efforts to resolve the Donbas conflict by peaceful means, one of the most striking features of the Minsk process is the tension between the short-term goal of stopping the fighting and the longer-term goal of reaching a lasting political settlement. The use of ambiguous language may have served the first purpose, but it may simultaneously have undermined the second by allowing the parties to believe that they are owed things that were, objectively speaking, incompatible.

In the present situation, there does not seem to be a "zone of possible agreement" between Ukraine and Russia. In the short to medium term, it is also difficult to see how the two parties, or third-party mediators, can create one. The possibility of a "Minsk III" solution to the conflict can be effectively ruled out, as President Zelensky has made clear on several occasions.

This is not to say that Ukraine's current political leadership rejects the idea of direct negotiations with Russia on how to end the war. But it is clear about the terms under which such negotiations may take place, and that the primary purpose of the negotiations must be to restore Ukraine's territorial integrity. The preconditions that Putin has set for pausing or ending his "special military operation" in Ukraine are clearly unacceptable for Zelensky. Ukraine is essentially being asked to accept not only the Russian demands that it rejected during the Istanbul talks in spring of 2022 (neutrality, non-alignment, limitations on the size of its armed forces, restrictions on foreign arms deliveries etc.), but also the territorial gains and claims that Russia has made since 2014.

The primary point of departure for the Ukrainian side has been the 10-point peace plan which was presented by president Zelensky at the G20 summit in Bali in November 2022. The plan placed strong emphasis on the need to restore Ukraine's territorial integrity and the country's internationally recognized borders. Zelensky's peace plan also called for the withdrawal of all Russian forces from the territory of Ukraine, the establishment of a special tribunal to prosecute Russian war crimes, and the issuance of reliable security guarantees. Without strong and credible security guarantees, a ceasefire is likely to be short-lived and vulnerable to collapse.

A "land for peace" deal, that is, one in which Ukraine cedes large parts of its internationally recognized land territory to Russia in exchange for peace, has long been considered unacceptable in Kyiv, as well as in most other European capitals. The concern is that such a deal could give Russia time to rebuild its military, only to try to take more of the country at a later stage. On top of this, a "land for peace" deal could embolden authoritarian states in other parts of the world which may want to attack or subjugate their neighbors.

As in 2014–2015, the future of the negotiation process will depend heavily on the battlefield dynamics. As the war stands now, Ukraine is defending well and continuing to inflict significant military losses on the Russian forces. But it is not currently capable of defeating the aggressor and regaining full control of its territory by military means. A Ukrainian military victory would require a significant increase in the Western military aid, and a further tightening of the international sanctions on Russia.

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